

The yellow color of the plants may disappear as the roots proliferate in the oxidized surface layer of the soil at the

end of tillering. Nonetheless yields are reduced because there are fewer tillers. Experiments on the response of rice

to sulfur applied in the paddy as ammonium sulfate, gypsum, and elemental sulfur are in progress. ❧

Effects of late sowing on dry-season rice in West Bengal

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Dry-season rice in West Bengal experiences low temperatures in the nursery and during early growth after transplanting. Nine local and introduced cultivars were sown on four dates representing the range used by local farmers (Table 1). Perhaps because the temperature remained at about 10°C throughout their nursery period, seedlings

sown on 6 and 26 December were shorter at all growth stages than the seedlings sown on 25 October and 15 November. Seedlings from all sowings produced only about one leaf for each 10 days of nursery growth. Seedling height varied more than leaf number.

In another experiment, dry-season and wet-season seedling heights were compared (Table 2). Sowings on 6 December and 26 December resulted in seedlings noticeably shorter than those from wet-season sowing. Final plant height, however, depended more on field temperatures after transplanting. ❧

Table 2. Effect of sowing date on rice seedling height and final plant height.^a West Bengal, India, 1976 dry season.

Nursery sowing date	Seedling ht ^b (% of wet-season ht)	Final plant ht (cm)
25 October	65.09	76.19
15 November	61.41	86.77
6 December	76.51	82.62
26 December	73.06	91.51

^aC.D. at 5%. 5.94; C.D. at 1%. 8.03.

^b20 days after sowing. Wetseason seedling ht, 21.94 cm.

Table 1. Relation of mean rice seedling height and number of leaves to sowing date of nine rice cultivars. West Bengal, India. dry season.

Plant age (DS) ^a	Nursery sowing date											
	Plant ht (cm)	25 October Leaves (no.)	25 October Av temp. (°C)	15 November Plant ht (cm)	15 November Leaves (no.)	15 November Av temp. (°C)	6 December Plant ht (cm)	6 December Leaves (no.)	6 December Av temp. (°C)	26 December Plant ht (cm)	26 December Leaves (no.)	26 December Av temp. (°C)
20	7.76	2.44	18.1	8.46	2.69	14.2	5.13	2.30	9.2	5.57	2.36	10.1
30	11.61	3.14	14.9	11.37	3.87	11.7	6.79	2.97	10.1	9.30	3.39	10.6
40	12.29	4.51	14.2	11.43	4.09	11.1	7.91	3.36	10.6	11.52	3.84	10.7

^aDays after sowing.

Udbatta disease and the application of nitrogen in paddy

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It has been said that heavy applications of nitrogen induce diseases. An experiment at Mandya confirmed that the incidence of Udbatta disease (*Ephelis oryzae* Syd) was generally much higher when nitrogen was applied at 100 kg/ha than when no nitrogen was applied (see table).

E. oryzae disease in rice (Cauvery) at various times and rates of nitrogen fertilizer application, Mandya, India, 1971.

Nitrogen (kg/ha)	Disease incidence (%) when N was applied at				Panicles (no./hill)	Disease incidence (%)
	Planting	Tillering	Panicle initiation	Booting		
000	0	0	0	0	8.9	2.5
100	100	0	0	0	10.5	4.1
100 ^a	100 ^a	0	0	0	12.4	4.6
100	75	25	0	0	13.5	5.4
100	75	0	25	0	13.1	5.5
100	75	0	25 ^b	0	11.8	5.2
100	75	0	0	25	12.1	5.6
100	50	25	25	0	13.4	6.1
100	50	0	25	25	12.6	5.2
100	25	25	25	25	12.3	6.4

^aSulfur-coated. C.D. at 5% highly significant. ^bFoliar spray.

The disease incidence also was higher when the nitrogen was given in split doses

than when it was applied basally; that result is unexplained. ❧